

Title: Omicron neutralization and the inference of correlates of protection based on anti-SARS-CoV-2 S-RBD IgG levels in boosted individuals

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Corresponding Author: Francesco Bonfante

First Author: Matteo Pagliari

Order of Authors

Matteo Pagliari, Eva Mazzetto, Michele Gastaldelli, Alessio Bortolami, Daniele Donà, Andrea Padoan, Costanza Di Chiara, Maria Diletta Pezzani, Chiara Cosma, Alessandra Napolitan, Erika Giorgia Quaranta, Edoardo Giussani, Alice Fusaro, Michela Pascarella, Ada Aita, Cecilia Liberati, Alessio Lorusso, Isabella Monne, Anita De Rossi, Daniela Basso, Stefano Porru, Antonia Ricci, Calogero Terregino, Mario Plebani, Evelina Tacconelli*, Carlo Giaquinto*, Francesco Bonfante*.

* Co-last authors

Region of origin: Italy

Research in context

Evidence before this study

A number of published and preprint papers has provided evidence of the reduced antibody neutralization of vaccinees for the SARS-CoV-2 omicron variant. These papers reported a beneficial effect of boosting on expansion of reactivity. To our knowledge, omicron neutralization data have not been analyzed to infer estimates of protection from infection and disease, but population-based correlates of protection have been suggested for SARS-CoV-2.

Added value of this study

In this study we present data on antibody neutralization against omicron and other variants deriving analytic serologic cut-offs that correlate with protection, using a common high-throughput assay targeting anti-SARS-CoV-2 Spike antibodies and relying on published models for the prediction of protection efficacy.

Implications of all the available evidence

We prove that a commercial assay might still be used upon thorough validation, to discriminate highly protected individuals, despite extreme antigenic variation of omicron. This finding is of immediate interest not only for immuno-bridging studies and non-inferiority comparisons for authorizing novel vaccines, but it is of practical application for any institution or medical professional interested in assessing the risk of infection and disease through widely available assays, at both individual and population level.

Summary

Background

The omicron variant has spread globally at unprecedented speed due to a combination of epidemiological and virological factors that still need to be fully unraveled. Although boosting of immunity in vaccinated populations has proven to increase the antibody recognition for this variant, we still ignore the impact that this intervention has on protection from infection and disease.

Methods

Relying on a live virus neutralization assay and a commercial chemiluminescence immunoassay targeting antibodies against the receptor binding domain (RBD) of the parental Spike protein, we tested the efficacy of homologous and heterologous booster vaccinations in inducing antibodies against SARS-CoV-2 parental, delta, beta and omicron variants by history of SARS-CoV-2 infection and age of population. Booster vaccination was performed with the BNT126b2 vaccine, while individuals who underwent heterologous booster vaccination were primed with the ChAdOx1 nCov-19 vaccine. Moreover, we studied the impact that prior immunity has on vaccination, in mildly infected individuals who received 2-3 doses of the BNT126b2 vaccine at different times after infection. Children previously infected with delta were evaluated 3.5 months after infection. To translate neutralization data into estimates of protection, we relied on published predictive models and inferred variant-specific thresholds of protection for both assays and assessed the accuracy of the commercial assay at identifying highly protected individuals.

Findings

We confirm that boosting significantly restores the ability of antibodies to recognize omicron and other variants, and that the homologous protocol with the BNT126b2 vaccine achieves higher and more broadly reactive neutralizing antibody titres, than those observed among individuals who crossed-over vaccines. On the other hand, mild prior infection with the parental virus and subsequent homologous vaccination with BNT126b2 induces high antibody levels, but with moderate breadth of response, while children aged 5-11 show negligible neutralizing antibodies against the omicron variant few months from infection. Neutralizing and binding antibodies correlate across all variants and allow the identification of variant-specific anti-RBD thresholds for 90% protection efficacy.

Interpretation

Boosting with the BNT126b2 vaccine is an immediate and effective measure to increase the protection against omicron, in naïve, as well as in previously infected individuals. Identification through serological commercial assays of thresholds of protection against the omicron and delta variants is a crucial step towards large-scale serosurveys to finely assess infection risk both at population and individual level.

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Introduction

Omicron was designated a COVID-19 variant of concern (VOC) by the World Health Organization (WHO) on 29 November 2021, about a week after the first identification of the virus, in South Africa (cit). The rapid spread of this variant and the unprecedented high number of amino acid mutations in the Spike (S) protein has prompted an immediate response from the scientific community to verify the ability of this variant to escape vaccine and infection-induced immunity, as well as its resistance to therapeutic antibodies. Preliminary findings report severe drops in antibody reactivity in vaccinated subjects and a general resistance of this variant to the majority of licensed monoclonal antibodies.¹⁻⁴ Scholars achieved consensus on the effect of boosters in partially restoring neutralization against omicron, but the extent of this phenomenon differed dramatically among the studies.^{1,5} Such variability might depend on substantial heterogeneity in the populations assessed, immunization-sampling intervals, different neutralization tests and lack of calibration with WHO international antibody standards (IS).⁶ Most importantly, in these studies little information can be found regarding estimates of protection against omicron and other variants. Despite an absolute correlate of protection is still not available for SARS-CoV-2, the elegant works by Khoury et al.⁷ and Earle et al.⁸ provided the necessary theoretical support for inferring correlates of protection, mainly relying on the normalization of neutralizing antibody titres of vaccinees against those obtained from sera of convalescent individuals.

In our study, we explored whether homologous and heterologous booster vaccination can induce neutralizing antibodies that correlate with protection against infection with parental, delta, beta and the omicron variants, in both naïve adults and convalescent adult and pediatric populations. In our study we paired live virus neutralization assays with a high-throughput chemiluminescence assay targeting the S receptor binding domain (RBD) to identify tentative cut-offs for large scale evaluations of protection.

Methods

The study aimed to assess the efficacy of homologous and heterologous booster vaccination in inducing neutralizing antibodies against infection with SARS-CoV-2 parental, delta, beta and omicron variants by history of SARS-CoV-2 infection and age of population. Subjects were enrolled from running prospective cohort studies established within the ORCHESTRA (Connecting European and International Cohorts to increase common and effective response to SARS-CoV2 Pandemic, H2020, <https://orchestra-cohort.eu/>) and the VERDI (SARS-CoV-2 variants Evaluation in pRegnancy and paeDIiatrics cohorts) projects. Both cohort studies included in their protocol the assessment of serological status (neutralizing antibody titres, NAT) in vaccinated adult population, with and without history of SARS-CoV-2 infection, at fixed time points. Information regarding ethical approvals, informed consent and cohort composition are found in the Supplementary material.

Study design

To test the effect of homologous and heterologous boosters, we analyzed immunity in 44 adult naïve individuals, 6 months after a two-dose BNT162b2 (BNT) cycle (2xBNT_{6M}; 14 subjects), 50 days after BNT homologous booster (2xBNT/BNT_{50D}; 14 subjects), and 22 days after ChAdOx1 nCov-19 (ChAd)/BNT162b2 heterologous booster (2xChAd/BNT_{22D}; 22 subjects). The impact of SARS-CoV-2 infections on immunity of vaccinated populations was tested in 22 subjects with history of mild SARS-CoV-2 infection developed in 2020, who received three or two doses of the BNT162b2 vaccine (Conv-2-3xBNT_{46D}). Within this group, 5 and 11 subjects received a two-dose + booster cycle at 65 and 312 days from infection, respectively, while a third subgroup of 6 subjects was primed around 123 days from infection and received a second booster dose at 225 days from priming. The 2xBNT_{6M} and the 2xBNT/BNT_{50D} each comprised 8 paired samples obtained from the same

individuals. A panel of 10 residual sera collected from HCW 12 days after BNT priming was included to provide multi-variant neutralization negative samples for ROC curves. For normalization purposes and to infer the predicted protective efficacy of NAT from vaccinated individuals, we included a cohort of 32 adults with history of mild/pauci-symptomatic infection in 2020.⁷

To assess whether a recent infection with the delta strain provides protection from the circulating variants in the pediatric population, we tested sera from 10 children aged 5-11, testing PCR positive, between July-August 2021, when the delta variant was dominant in Italy (DeltaChildren_{3.5M}).⁹ Children were sampled at a median of 100 days from infection. The characteristics of the different groups and of each individual are presented in the supplementary material (Tab 1, S1 and S2).

We tested all sera by live virus neutralization against the parental, the beta, the delta and the omicron variants and by a high-throughput chemiluminescence assay.

Viruses

The parental SARS-CoV-2 strain hCoV-19/Italy/PD_20VIR1935i-P4-L/2020 was isolated during the first wave of the pandemic in March 2020, during routine diagnostic activities conducted at the University Hospital of Padua (Italy).¹⁰ The delta SARS-CoV-2 strain hCoV-19/Italy/ABR-IZSGC288699/2021, lineage B.1.617.2 was kindly provided by Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale dell'Abruzzo e del Molise (Italy).¹¹ The beta SARS-CoV-2 strain hCoV-19/Netherlands/NoordHolland_10159/2021, lineage B.1.351, was obtained from the European Virus Archive goes Global (EVAg). The omicron SARS-CoV-2 virus was detected during routine genomic surveillance activities of the Regione Veneto program at the Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale delle Venezie (Italy).¹² Details about the isolation, propagation and sequencing of viruses are reported in the Supplementary material.

Focus Reduction Neutralization Test

Sera were heat-inactivated and serially diluted in DMEM and incubated with an equal volume of virus at 37° C for 1 hour. Antibody-virus mixture was added to Vero E6 cells in duplicate and incubated at for 1 hour. Post incubation, the inoculum was removed and 100 µl of overlay solution of Minimum essential medium (MEM), 2% FBS, penicillin (100 U/ml), streptomycin (100 U/ml) and 0.8% carboxy methyl cellulose was added to each well. Plates were incubated at 37° C for 20 hours (for the parental virus, beta, and delta variants) or 28 hours (Omicron variant). After incubation, the overlay was removed and cells were fixed with 4% paraformaldehyde in PBS for 30 minutes. Visualization of plaques was obtained as previously described.¹³ Foci were visualized on BioSpot™ (CTL Europe GmbH). The serum neutralization titre was defined as the reciprocal of the highest dilution resulting in a reduction of the control focus count >50% (FRNT₅₀). Negative samples were assigned an arbitrary value of 10. Tests were run in duplicate.

Anti S-RBD chemiluminescence assay

Samples were tested for the presence of antibodies binding the RBD of the S protein using the chemiluminescence immunoassay (CLIA) anti-SARS-CoV-2 S-RBD IgG Ab (Snibe Diagnostics, New Industries Biomedical Engineering Co., Ltd [Snibe], Shenzhen, China). The assay presents a high linearity when validation was carried out on convalescent individuals in 2020, with clinical sensitivity and specificity of 96.9% and 91.8%, respectively.¹³

The manufacturer's claimed cut-offs for positivity are 1.0 kAU/L or 4.33 kBAU/L.

Protection thresholds and ROC curves

To determine a neutralization threshold that would categorize individuals as highly protected, we determined the NAT estimated to grant a 90% protection efficacy (PE) from infection, based on the population-based predictive models for vaccine efficacy by Khoury et al. and Earle et al.^{7,8} To assess the impact of variant antigenic mismatches on protection from infection in groups, we applied the predictive model for vaccine efficacy by Khoury et al. Details on the application of these models are reported in the Supplementary materials. To assess the ability of anti-RBD antibody binding concentrations to predict neutralizing titres that correlate with protection from variant infection, we performed receiver operating characteristic (ROC) analyses on variant-specific FRNT₅₀ titres and the corresponding BAU/ml values. We determined optimal cut-offs that maximized specificity over sensitivity, hypothesizing a use of high-throughput CLIA assays in the context of large-scale hospital serological screening, rather than for diagnostic purposes.

True positives were calculated as samples that were either neutralization positive (≥ 20) or with titres \geq threshold of 90% PE.

Data processing and statistical analyses

GraphPad Prism 9.1.2 (GraphPad Software) was used to draw figures and perform statistical analyses. Statistical significances and confidence intervals were calculated using the tests described below each figure. Mean fold-changes in neutralization titres were first calculated for each sample and then averaged. Predictions of protective efficacy were carried out under R environment utilizing the original data and script from Khoury et al. and made available on GitHub.¹⁴

Role of the funding source

The funder had no role in the study design, data collection, data analysis, data interpretation, writing of the manuscript, or the decision to submit.

Results

All SARS-CoV-2 were confirmed by sequencing as belonging to lineage B.1 (parental), B.1.351 (beta), AY.122 (delta), and BA.1 (omicron) and differed substantially in their plaquing morphology (Fig. S1). The delta virus carried the T274I and R682W amino acidic substitutions at the level of the S protein, currently reported in a minority of the deposited sequences (Tab. S3).

Infection-naïve individuals in the 2xBNT_{6M} group showed barely detectable neutralizing antibodies against omicron (geometric mean titres (GMT) 14), recording a 28-fold drop in reactivity compared to the parental virus (Fig. 1). Despite a 3-fold drop in delta neutralization, the majority of subjects (86%) had detectable neutralizing antibodies against this variant. Homologous and heterologous boosts in infection-naïve individuals achieved the desirable effect of significantly ($p < 0.05$) increasing neutralizing titres against the four strains (Fig. 1B, C). In particular, in the 2xBNT/BNT_{50D} group the GMTs for the beta, delta and omicron variants were 651, 881 and 200, which represent a minimum of a 10-fold increase for each variant compared to the 2xBNT_{6M} group, while the boosting in the 2xChAd/BNT_{22D} group achieved lower GMTs of 429, 694 and 102 against the same variants. Besides recording overall higher neutralization across all variants, homologous boosting expanded the breadth of response in particular for the omicron virus reaching a 9.9-fold mismatch, while the 2xChAd/BNT_{22D} recorded a high 20.0-fold mismatch. The broader reactivity observed in the 2xBNT/BNT_{50D} group includes also the beta and delta variants, which resulted to have lower antigenic mismatches than the ones recorded in 2xChAd/BNT_{22D}. In a subject-matched comparison of 8 individuals (Fig. 1F), the broadening effect of the homologous BNT booster was demonstrated by the significantly higher fold-increase in NAT recorded for the beta (30x), delta (38) and omicron (50x) variants, compared to the parental increase (26x).

Individuals with history of mildly-symptomatic parental virus infection in 2020, proved that 2-3 doses of the BNT vaccine induced the highest NAT of all groups (Fig. 1D). Nonetheless, the antigenic reactivity of these sera closely resembled that observed in 2xChAd/BNT_{22D}, as sera reacted relatively poorly with omicron, given the high 19.9-fold mismatch in neutralization. Although 50% of boosted individuals in this group had been vaccinated 10 months from infection, other 5 and 6 individuals had been vaccinated two and four months post infection, respectively (Fig. S2). These latter subgroups recorded consistently lower GMT against all viruses.

In our study, mildly affected COVID-19 cases with a median age of 39 (16-60) had a GMT of 83.5. The threshold estimated to confer a protection from infection with $\geq 90\%$ efficacy resulted to be 151. On the other hand, our lowest neutralization titre of 20 corresponded to an estimated 89% protection from severe diseases. Setting the highest threshold, we observed that before the booster, none of the subjects in the 2xBNT_{6M} group resulted highly protected against infection with omicron, while 50% were protected for delta (Fig. 2A). Homologous and heterologous boosting dramatically improved the outlook among infection-naïve individuals, recording 94% and 92% of highly protected individuals against the delta virus, respectively. On the other hand, the same groups comprised of only 71% and 54% highly protected individuals against the omicron variant. Convalescent and vaccinated subjects with 2-3 doses of BNT scored the highest proportion of highly protected subjects against delta and 64% against omicron. When the threshold of 20 was set, in the 2xBNT_{6M} group the proportion of individuals protected from severe diseases from delta and omicron was 86% and 21%, respectively, while approximately all boosted individuals resulted protected from severe disease, irrespective of variant.

Children previously infected with delta with a median age of 8 years (5-10) and an infection-sampling interval of 101 days (66-125) recorded homologous GMT of 76, while the GMT against omicron and beta variants were close to negativity with values of 14 and 11 (Fig. 1E), respectively. We avoided to calculate a proportion of highly protected subjects in children given that the models were developed on efficacy trials of adult populations.

For each group, GMTs were used as parameters for the predictive model by Khoury et al. to obtain estimates of PE from infection. Six months after the BNT full cycle, a modest 36% (95% CI 23 – 43) protection from omicron was estimated, while 83% (95% CI 80 – 86) protection was predicted against delta (Fig. S3). Irrespective of naiveness to infection, after homologous boosting, the predicted PE against omicron was 93% (95% CI 90 – 95), while the heterologous booster reached 86% (95% CI 83 – 89) predicted PE. For all boosted groups, PE from delta infection ranged between 98-99%.

We verified whether a high-throughput anti-RBD CLIA assay retained semi-quantitative characteristics against omicron, beta and delta. Our correlation analyses run on the totality of sera confirmed that despite severe drops in neutralization and antibody binding reactivity, quantification of anti-RBD antibodies against omicron correlated with NAT ($r=0.7530$; $p<0.0001$), similarly to the other variants (Fig. 2C). When ROC curves were generated with “positive neutralization” set at the highest threshold of 151, the area under the curve (AUC) was comparably high for the parental (0.98), beta (1.00), delta (0.96) and omicron (0.96) variants ($p<0.0001$). With analyses set to maximize specificity, the threshold corresponded to a cut-off of 188.5 BAU/ml for both delta and parental viruses, with identical specificity (Sp) and sensitivity (Se) of 93% and 95% (95%CI, 78-100), respectively. For more divergent variants, cut-offs increased substantially to 809 BAU/ml with 98% Se and 94% Sp for beta (95%CI, 81-99), and 2208 BAU/ml with 75% Se and 95% Sp for omicron (95%CI, 86-99). Setting “positive neutralization” at the lowest possible threshold of 20, cut-offs for parental, delta, beta and omicron were 44.5 BAU/ml, 44.5 BAU/ml, 77.5 BAU/ml and 274.5 BAU/ml, respectively (Fig. 2B). To provide additional elements for the assessment of the discriminative ability of the anti-RBD assay, we tested the correlation between NAT against the

parental virus and NAT against omicron and delta (Fig. S4). Despite the expected shift in slopes, correlations were high for both delta ($r=0.81$, $p<0.0001$) and omicron ($r=0.79$, $p<0.0001$). Moreover, these two viruses shared good correlation also when tested against each other ($r=0.73$, $p<0.0001$). To further assess the ability of this assay to perform fine quantifications of neutralizing antibodies against variants, we calculated fold-changes of mean binding values and observed surprisingly close patterns to the ones recorded by FRNT (Fig. S5).

Discussion

Omicron has proven to be the most diffusive SARS-CoV-2 virus studied so far. It is still not clear whether the ability to spread at unprecedented speed is the result of waning immunity in vaccinated populations, or a combination of significant immune escape and high transmissibility. In our study, we generated data to help assess the protective efficacy of both vaccine and infection-induced humoral immunity against the omicron, delta and beta variants. We targeted cohorts homogenous in terms of immunization-sampling intervals and clinical presentations, and with known immune status for SARS-CoV-2. We confirm that six months after a full cycle with the BNT vaccine, the antigenic mismatch with omicron is equal to 28x and higher than ever recorded for previous VOCs.¹⁵ Homologous boosting with BNT induced not only the expected robust humoral response towards the parental virus, but also expanded the breadth of reactivity, a result in agreement with the majority of the manuscripts available.^{3,16,17} This phenomenon was particularly relevant for omicron, as the mismatch in this group was reduced, due to a 50x increase in NAT. In contrast, we did not observe a comparable expansion in reactivity when heterologous boosting was applied with BNT, crossing-over with the ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 vaccine, despite the similar NAT between these groups. These results are in keeping with the 49.9x increase in omicron neutralization described by Dejnirattisai et al. in a comparable cohort.¹⁸ Moreover, Garcia-Beltran et al. observed a lower expansion of NAT against both omicron and delta, after Ad26.COV2.S/BNT boosting than after BNT homologous boosting. In the same manuscript, greater antigenic mismatch was observed in subjects boosted with a second dose of the Ad26.COV2.S than in groups receiving a third dose of the BNT vaccine, speculating that mRNA vaccination might provide overall broader reactivity than adenovirus-vectored vaccination.¹⁹

Interestingly, when we tested sera from a cohort of subjects previously infected with the parental virus and triple-vaccinated with BNT, despite recording the highest NAT for all variants, the breadth of response was almost identical to that observed in the 2xChAd/BNT_{22D} group. At the time of writing, only Carreno et al. tested cohorts comparable to ours with infection-naïve and convalescent BNT triple-vaccinated individuals. In their study they found that 20 days from boosting, the fold-drop in reactivity for beta and omicron was greater for the convalescents, despite reaching similar GMTs of infection-naïve subjects.²⁰ We speculate that when immunity is primed by infection, the expansion of reactivity observed in naïve individuals after boosting might be compromised due to *original antigenic sin* biasing the response towards selected epitopes that are poorly cross-reactive with variants, possibly leading to a reduction of the affinity maturation process. Nonetheless, this phenomenon might be susceptible to several variables, as proven by contrasting results reported before the omicron emergence.^{21,22}

Recently published models identified thresholds for both neutralizing antibody titres and anti-spike antibody concentrations that correlate with protective efficacy against infection with the ancestral virus.^{7,8,23} In these studies, NAT from phase I/II studies and protective efficacies observed during phase III studies were computed to model the prediction of protection. To compensate for variability in the adopted serological assays, each dataset was normalized against the reported titres of convalescent individuals. Recent work by Cromer et al., proves that in vitro neutralization of variants strongly correlates with real-world data on PE against infection, and that even homologous NAT to

the ancestral virus are sufficient to predict protection from variants if antigenic mismatches are known.²⁴ We used a hybrid approach in our study, relying on these models to infer a neutralization correlate of 90% PE from infection for the ancestral virus, to subsequently apply this threshold to neutralization data generated against variants. We observed that before boosting, the model predicted 34% PE. On the other hand, a triple dose of BNT dramatically improved the response, granting across all groups a predicted PE ranging between 86%-93% for omicron, and even higher for delta. Estimating the duration of a status of “high protection” was beyond our scopes, but it is important to highlight that these predictive models were developed based on efficacies estimated over 3-5 months after vaccination. This aspect is of importance considering that our cohorts were sampled from 22 to 50 days from boosting and that immunity wanes at different rates over the first months from immunization.²⁵ Although limited to only 10 children, our assessment delivered important results regarding the neutralization ability of pediatric populations in the 5-11 years range who have an history of mild COVID-19 infection. Despite vaccination is now approved in children, the coverage is still low. We tested children previously infected with delta and verified that after 3-4 months from infection, only a minority of subjects had NAT potentially protective from delta infection. An even less protective profile was evident for the omicron variant. These results were expected given the interval from infection and the age of children, but are an important reminder of the effectiveness that vaccines have compared to natural mild infection in eliciting high NAT.^{26,27}

WHO has made available IS to help achieve standardization of serological results, but a rapid update is needed to provide variant-specific reagents.⁶ We tested the hypothesis that existing semi-quantitative anti-spike and anti-RBD assays can be accurate at inferring correlates of protection for the circulating variants. Setting a 90% PE threshold and maximizing specificity, a commercial anti-RBD CLIA assay identified an optimal cut-off of 188.5 BAU/ml for the parental virus, falling in the same range of the 151 BAU/ml threshold established by Goldblatt et al. for an estimated 83% PE.²³ On the other hand, Feng et al, reported a correlate of 506 BAU/ml for an anti-RBD assay associated with 80% protection with the ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 vaccine against the alpha variant.²⁸ Given the good correlations between FRNT and CLIA, we consider acceptable optimal cut-offs of 2208 BAU/ml for omicron and 809 BAU/ml for beta. Our data aligns well with work by Garcia-Bernard et al. who drew similar conclusions using a CLIA assay and pseudovirus neutralizations, although recording considerably higher values.²⁹ When we compared BAU by variant specific neutralization titres, the assay delivered unexpectedly close fold-changes to the ones observed with the neutralization assay, a result that is in keeping with fold-change derived for the delta variant by Goldblatt et al. when testing sera with variant specific S antigens.²³ As clearly stated by the WHO in the instructions for use of IS reagents, comparison of results expressed as BAU/ml is cautioned when dealing with assays targeting different antigens (e.g. trimeric Spike, RBD, S1). Besides, even after calibration to BAU/ml, assays targeting the same antigen might fluctuate significantly in their correlation, reminding us of the complexity of the harmonization process.³⁰ Nonetheless, our data suggest that upon further validation, the use of these assays might still be considered.

Our study has several limitations, some of which are intrinsic to the predictive models applied. Our cohort of triple-vaccinated HCW is composed almost entirely by women. Although enrollees were on average 49-years old, we cannot exclude that the higher and broader neutralization observed in this group might depend in part on sex differences, even if higher antibodies after vaccination were reported for females >60 years of age, and not in younger cohorts^{31,32}. Moreover, our convalescent cohort resembles closely the one reported by Walsh et al. in the immunogenicity study of the BNT126b2 vaccine, both for the severity of disease and for mean NAT. Nonetheless, our median interval time for the collection of sera after infection was of 51 days and we ignore whether this time corresponds to those in the studies used to develop the model.

Although our cut-off for variants are reported in BAU/ml, these values are obtained applying the conversion recommended by the manufacturer, and no information is available regarding the standardization exercises that generated this conversion factor. We caution against application of these cut-offs with serological assays targeting different isotypes and/or antibodies against different viral antigens, since our data were not harmonized internally through use of WHO IS and in light of the limited number of sera tested in this study.

In conclusion, this is the first study to indicate correlates for protection against the omicron variant expressed as binding antibody units. These cut-offs were obtained with a widely available commercial platform using a kit designed around the parental spike antigen, proving that commercial assays might still be used upon thorough validation, despite the circulation of variants. This finding is of immediate interest not only for immuno-bridging studies and non-inferiority comparisons for authorizing novel vaccines, but it has practical value for institutions and healthcare professionals interested in assessing the risk of infection and disease in a given population through titration of antibodies.

Our study adds substantially to the recent evidence, suggesting boosting with currently available mRNA vaccines, as one of the most immediate and effective responses we have to combat the omicron wave. We believe that besides a rapid development and roll-out of variants-adjusted vaccines, an update of serological assays is urgently needed in the coming months, since monitoring the immune status of populations will be key in effectively developing vaccination schedules by individuals 's infection risk.

Data sharing

Individual neutralization and antibody binding raw data together with ROC analyses datasets will be made available from the corresponding author on Article publication, to researchers with a reasonable request.

Contributors

FB, MP, ET and CG conceived and conceptualized the study. CDC, AP, DD, AL, MDP, AA, DB, SP, MPas, CC, CL, ADR, and AR contributed to sample collection, MP, EM, AB, AP and AN performed experiments, FB, MP, EM, MG, AF, EGQ, CC, EG analyzed data, FB, MP, EM, IM, CT, AP, ET, CG, AR, ADR, MPle contributed to data interpretation, FB, ET, CG, MP and MG wrote the first draft. All authors contributed to the manuscript and approved the final version of the article. All authors could access all of the data in the study and the corresponding author had responsibility for protecting the dataset. FB, ET, CG and MP were responsible for the decision to submit the manuscript.

Declaration of interest

The authors have no conflict of interest.

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the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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Figure legends

Figure 1 Neutralization of omicron compared to parental, beta and delta viruses in different cohorts.

Results for focus reduction neutralization tests. Neutralization assays were performed with the use of live viruses, including three variants and the parental virus harbouring the D614G mutation. Serum samples were obtained from people who received 2 doses of BNT162b2 (A, n=14, 6 months after the second dose), 2 doses of BNT162b2 plus BNT162b2 booster (B, n=17, 50 days after booster), 2 doses of ChAdOx1 plus BNT162b2 booster (C, n=13, 22 days after booster), 2 or 3 doses of BNT162b2 after recovering from parental virus infection (D, n=22, 45 days after last dose). Panel E indicate neutralization titres of convalescent sera obtained from children recovered from delta infection (n=10, 3·5 months post infection onset). The raw data and information regarding donors (sex, age, severity of disease in case of convalescent sera, and dates of vaccinations and sampling) of serum samples are summarized in Table 1 in the Supplementary. The heights of the bars and the numbers over the bars indicate the geometric mean titres, and the I bars indicate 95% confidence intervals. The numbers in parentheses indicate the mean fold-reduction in the neutralization titres against the parental virus. In panel A, omicron fold-reduction is highlighted in red to indicate that sera neutralizing the parental virus < 1:160 were censored for this calculation, in order to avoid underestimation of antigenic distances due to low starting titres. The horizontal dashed lines indicate the limit of detection. Panel F shows FRNT₅₀ titres against the parental virus, beta, delta, and omicron variants, for subject-matched samples collected 6 months after the second BNT162b2 dose and 50 days after the BNT162b2 booster. The numbers in parentheses indicate the mean fold-increase in neutralization after the booster dose. Each data point represent a single sample and indicate the 50% neutralization titre obtained for each sample against the indicated virus.

Friedman test with Dunn's multiple comparison was performed. *p<0·0332, ** p<0·0021, *** p<0·0002, **** p<0·0001

Figure 2 Protection thresholds for neutralizing and anti-RBD binding antibody levels.

A) Neutralization titres against the delta and omicron variants across all groups. Percentages above each bar show the proportion of individuals estimated to protected from infection with a 90% probability (in blue), and from severe disease with a 89% probability (in red). The two thresholds were calculated as described within the Method section. The heights of the bars indicate the geometric mean titres, and the I bars indicate 95% confidence intervals. Points represents the FRNT₅₀ titres of individual sera. B) Anti-RBD antibody levels measured with the Maglumi chemiluminescence immunoassay (CLIA) anti-SARS-CoV-2 S-RBD IgG Ab were plotted against neutralization titres of parental, beta, delta and omicron. Vertical dotted lines indicate for each variant the optimal cut-off for the identification of sera with neutralization titres \geq than the respective thresholds indicated by the horizontal color-coded lines. C) Correlation between FRNT₅₀ titres and anti-RBD binding antibody levels for each sample. Simple linear regression model was calculated and Pearson's correlation coefficient is indicated for each dataset.

Tables

Table 1 Information regarding groups for whom neutralization assays were performed against all viruses

Cohorts	2xChAd/BNT _{22D}	2xBNT _{6M}	2xBNT/ BNT _{50D}	Conv- 2-3xBNT _{46D}	DeltaChildren _{3.5M}
Previous COVID-19 (WHO stages) (median, range)	NA	NA	NA	2 (1-2)	2 (1-2)
Total	13	14	17	22	10
Sex (%female)	54	86	94	59	50
Age (y) (median, range)	56 (28-66)	37 (27-66)	49 (27-66)	36 (29-63)	8 (5-10)
Infection-1st dose interval (median, range)	NA	NA	NA	210 (44-360)	NA
1st-2nd dose interval (median, range)	79 (78-88)	21	21 (21-33)	22 (16-236)	NA
2nd-3rd dose interval (median, range)	186 (170-193)	NA	274 (216-285)	256 (151-281)	NA
Sampling days post last dose (median, range)	22 (17-31)	191 (157-247)	50 (22-82)	46 (24-63)	NA
Sampling days post-infection onset (median, range)	NA	NA	NA	NA	101 (66-125)

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Proportion of individuals predicted to be protected from infection and severe disease

